

ANALYSIS OF GROUND WATER QUALITY AND ITS PHYSICO - CHEMICAL PROPERTIES IN RURAL REGION OF DAVANGERE DISTRICT, KARNATAKA, INDIA

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Abstract - Groundwater quality with the availability of clean and safe groundwater is critical for public health as well as sustainable development. Over the past few years, reducing groundwater quality has become an emerging issue, especially in rural regions. The present study analyses the groundwater quality of Kathige village, which is situated in the Davangere district of Karnataka. Seven groundwater samples were sampled and analysed for major physico-chemical parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, calcium, magnesium, sodium, carbonate, bicarbonate, chloride, sodium adsorption ratio, and residual sodium carbonate. The findings revealed that some of the parameters—especially Total Hardness, Total Dissolved Solids, Electric Conductivity, pH, and Chloride—were above the limits set by Bureau of Indian Standards for potable water, making the water unfit for household consumption. Nevertheless, the quality is within acceptable levels for irrigation purposes. The high levels of nitrates, phosphates, and trace metals imply contamination due to agricultural runoff as well as poor sewerage management. The results underscore the necessity for continuous monitoring of groundwater quality and the observance of proper waste disposal mechanisms to avert further deterioration.

Keywords: Degradation, Ground Water Contamination, Kathige, Rainwater Harvest, Water Pollution.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Groundwater contamination due to leachate arising from solid waste disposal has become a serious issue as it affects the environment, health of people concerned and social wellbeing. A thorough analysis needs to be carried out to arrive at a sustainable and possible solution for mitigating the groundwater pollution due to solid waste disposal^[1]. This includes methods of waste disposal, characterization of leachate and groundwater quality, lithology variation, groundwater flow and contaminant transport modelling, health and social issues of the people depending on the contaminated water^[2].

Ground water is the water that seeps through rocks and soil and is stored below the ground. The rocks in which ground water is stored are called aquifers. Aquifers are typically made up of gravel, sand, sandstone or limestone. Water moves through these rocks because they have large connected spaces that make them permeable^[3]. The area where water fills the aquifer is called the saturated zone. The depth from the surface at which ground water is found is called the water table. The water table can be as shallow as a foot below the ground or it can be a few hundred meters deep^{[4][5]}. Heavy rains can cause the water table to rise and conversely, continuous extraction of ground water can cause the level to fall.

1.1. Groundwater scenario in India

Groundwater in India is become a critical resource. However, an increasing number of aquifers are reaching unsustainable levels of exploitation. India is the largest users of groundwater in the world. It uses an estimated 230 cubic kilometres of groundwater per year - over a quarter of the global total. More than 60% of irrigated agriculture and 85% of drinking water supplies are dependent on groundwater (Ground water board, 2017)^[6].

1.2. Groundwater pollution

Groundwater pollution occurs when pollutants are released to the ground and make their way down into groundwater. This type of water pollution can also occur naturally due to the presence of a minor and unwanted constituent, contaminant or impurity in the groundwater, in which case it is more likely referred to as contamination rather than pollution. Pollution can occur from on-site sanitation systems, landfills, effluent from wastewater treatment plants, leaking sewers, petrol filling stations or from over application of fertilizers in agriculture^[8]. Pollution (or contamination) can also occur from naturally occurring contaminants, such as arsenic or fluoride^{[7][9]}.

1.3. Effect on human health

Contaminated groundwater can cause a vast number of different illnesses to humans, plants and animals. The pollution is such that if a human eats plants or animals that have been contaminated, they will be ingesting the harmful chemicals as well. A person may think they have an average bout of food poisoning when they are actually suffering side effects of contaminated water. Exposure to these can cause damage to the brain and nervous systems. Kidney damage is also associated with heavy lead and chromium exposure. Children are more susceptible because of their small sizes. These health problems are permanent and irreversible^[10]. A person needs an experienced attorney to fight for the right compensation for this kind of damage. Regular flu symptoms that may go unnoticed include headache, nausea, fatigue, rashes, and eye irritation. Excessive or long-term exposure can lead to death^[11].

1.4. Solid waste landfill site

This municipal solid waste normally termed as “garbage” is an inevitable by-product of human activity which is disposed through dumping. Solid waste land filling is the most common method of solid waste disposal. The landfill consists of municipal solid wastes and these wastes are known as trash or garbage. The waste dump constituents include wastes from domestic such as kitchen wastes, clothes, cardboards, plastic, glass, paper etc. Municipal solid wastes also include construction wastes such as bricks, concrete, sand and adding on wastes from fish markets and vegetable markets^[12].

1.5. Effect of solid waste landfill site

Open dumps are unsightly, unsanitary, and generally smelly. They attract scavenging animals, rats, insects, pigs and other pests. Surface water percolating through the trash can dissolve out or leach harmful chemicals that are then carried away from the dumpsites in surface or subsurface runoff. Among these chemicals heavy metals are particularly insidious and lead to the phenomenon of bioaccumulation and bio-magnifications^[14]. These heavy metals may constitute an environmental problem, if the leachate percolate into the ground water. The presence of bore well at the landfill sites to draw ground water threatens to contaminate the ground water^[13].

1.6. Present scenario of solid waste

Overall dumping rate all over the world is found to be 1.3 billion tons per year and are expected to increase to approximately 2.2 billion tons per year by 2025 and Metro cities in India generate about 30,000 tonnes of waste per day and Class I cities about 50,000 tonnes per day. The dumped wastes when coming in contact with the moisture tends to extract organic and inorganic substances from trash into liquid which is known as leachate^[15].

1.7 Effect of leachate on groundwater

A water pollutant is a chemical or physical substance present in it at the excessive levels capable of causing harm to living organisms. The physical hazards are the dissolved solids and suspended solids^[16]. The chemical hazards are the copper, manganese, lead, cadmium, phosphate, nitrate etc. As the public health concern, the ground water should be free from physical and chemical hazards. The people in and around the dumping site are depending upon the ground water for drinking and other domestic purposes. The soil pollution arises due to the leaching of wastes from landfills and the most common pollutant involved is the metals like copper, lead, cadmium, mercury etc., The Contamination of ground water and soil is the major environmental risk related to unsanitary land filling of solid waste^[17].

1.7. Effect of heavy metals on human health

Environmental contamination and exposure to heavy metals such as mercury, cadmium and lead is a serious growing problem throughout the world. Human exposure to heavy metals has risen dramatically in the last 50 years as a result of an exponential increase in the use of heavy metals in industrial processes and products^{[19][20]}. Heavy metals can directly influence behaviour by impairing mental and neurological function, influencing neurotransmitter production and utilization, and altering numerous metabolic body processes^[18]. Systems in which toxic metal elements can induce impairment and dysfunction include the blood and cardiovascular, eliminative pathways (colon, liver, kidneys, skin), endocrine (hormonal), energy production pathways, enzymatic, gastrointestinal, immune, nervous (central and peripheral), reproductive, and urinary. The adverse effects of excess accumulation of HM are well documented. The dissertation work on the groundwater quality analysis in the Mandur solid waste dumpsite area was taken to understand the ground water gets contaminated due to the dumping of solid waste^[21].

2.0. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area – KATHIGE

Kathige village is located in Honnali Taluq of Davengere district in Karnataka, India. It is situated 15km away from Honnali Taluq. The total geographical area of village is 1651.87 hectares. Kathige has a total population of 2103 peoples. There are about 419 houses in Kathige village. Honnali is nearest town to Kathige which is approximately 15km away (Fig.1).

Fig. 1- Aerial view of kathige village

2.2. Sampling area

A total of eight villages were covered for ground water samples collected from Kathige, Jeenahalli, Madenahalli and jeenahalli cross which belongs to Kathige gram panchayath. The area is geographically lies between 75°5N longitude and 14.14°E Latitude longitude with altitude of 657m.

2.3. Drainage

Tunga and Bhadra Rivers draining in majority of the district and south Shivamogga and Davengere.

2.4. Agriculture and Crops

Agriculture is the main occupation of the district. The major crops grown in the district are Paddy, Ragi, Jowar, Bajra, Maize and Wheat. Pulses like Gram, Niger are also cultivated along with oilseed like Groundnut, sunflower. Different varieties of fruits and vegetables are also produced (GWIB, 2020).

2.5. Rainfall and climate

The rainfall of the district is accounted by the Pre monsoon (PRE), SW monsoon (SWM) and NE monsoon (NEM). Majority of the rainfall is contributed by SW Monsoon. In general, humid to semiarid climatic conditions prevail in the district. The average temperature is around 23.1°C. The seasonal and annual normal rainfall of the taluk from the year 2011 to 2020 is considered for studying the rainfall pattern. The annual rainfall of Kathige is 556mm (GWIB, 2020) [22].

2.6. Geomorphology and soil types

South east forming pediplains interspersed with hills all along the western part. The pediplains are the underlain by granites and gneisses with the highest elevation of 850 to 950 MSL. The pediplain constitute low relief area having matured dissected rolling topography with erosion land slope covered by a layer of red loamy soil of varied thickness. The pediplains is dissected by streamlets flowing in southern direction (GWIB, 2020) [22].

The soils of the districts can be broadly grouped into red loamy soil and lateritic soil.

- i) **Red loamy and sandy soils** generally occur on hilly to undulating land slope on granite and gneissic terrain. The soils are light textured and are highly leached in nature with good infiltration rate. It is mainly seen in the Mandur village.
- ii) **Laterite soils** occur on undulating terrain forming plain to gently sloping topography of peninsular gneissic region. It is mainly covered in south eastern part of the village (GWIB, 2020).

2.7. Ground Water Scenario

Ground water occurs in phreatic conditions or unconfined conditions in the weathered zone and under semi confined to confined conditions in fractured and jointed rock formations. The occurrence of Ground water movement and recharge to aquifers are controlled by various factors like fracture pattern, degree of weathering, geo-morphological setup and amount of rainfall received.

Generally, the depth of weathering varies, being more in the valley, and often extending up to 30 m in the dug wells. However, the yield in the bore well is dependent upon factors like degree of weathering, presence of joints and fractures and its connectivity and the presence of intrusive bodies (GWIB, 2012) [23].

2.8. Behaviour of ground water level

Behaviour of ground water level is essentially controlled by physiography, lithology and rainfall. Ground water level behaviour is analysed based on monitoring of ground water level from the network hydrograph stations (NHS) established by CGWB. In Bangalore urban district, there are 22 NHS and 13 piezometers, which are monitored four times in a year during May, August, November & January.

The depth to water level in the core area of Mandur village has the shallowest water level in the range of (1-5) m bgl. Majority of the stations located in the periphery has deeper water level in the range of 10- 20 m bgl. In general, pre monsoon depth to water levels of the piezometer ranges from 5 to 30 m bgl. In dug wells, it ranges from 2 to 11 m. The post monsoon depth to water level ranges of the piezometer varies from 2 to 40 m bgl. Indugwells, it ranges from 0.5 to 11 m. Long-term water level trend The behaviour of long-term water level trend in ground water level has been arrived at based on NHS data during the decade 2011- 2020. The presents the decadal water level fluctuation [24].

2.9. Sampling

The Preliminary survey was carried out to identify sampling point around the study area. The water samples were collected and preserved as per standard method APHA, 2002. Seven samples were collected within two weeks intervals during the month of April 2022.

2.10. Sampling locations

No.	Sample Location	Longitude	Latitude	Altitude
S1	Kathige	14°15"N	75°5"E	657m
S2	Anjaneya Temple Kathige	14°15"N	75°5"E	657m
S3	Jeenahalli cross	14°15"N	75°5"E	657m
S4	Madenahalli	14°15"N	75°5"E	657m
S5	Venkateshwara Temple	14°15"N	75°5"E	657m
S6	Jeenahalli	13°85"N	75°5"E	657m
S7	Dairy Jeenahalli	13°85"N	75°5"E	657m

2.11. Physio-chemical analysis of water

Good quality of water is essential for living organisms. The quality of water was assessed by studying its physical and chemical characteristics. The details of methods used for physicochemical analysis of ground water are given below (Table 1).

Table 1. Methods used for physic-chemical analysis of ground water sample

Sl. No.	Parameters	Method used	IS 10500:2012
1	Electrical Conductance ($\mu\text{mhos/cm}$)	Electrode	1000 $\mu\text{S/cm}$
2	Total Dissolved Solids (mg/L)	Gravimetry	1000mg/L
3	pH	Electrode	6.5-8.5
4	Chloride (mg/L)	Argentometric method	1000mg/L
5	Alkalinity (mg/L)	titrimetric method	200mg/L
6	Total Hardness (mg/L)	EDTA method	600mg/L
7	Calcium Hardness (mg/L)	EDTA method	200mg/L
8	Magnesium Hardness (mg/L)	Calculation	100mg/L
9	Sulphates (mg/L)	Barium chloride	400mg/L
10	Nitrate (mg/L)	Phenoldisulphonic method	45mg/L
11	Fluorides (mg/L)	SPANDS Method	1.5mg/L
12	Phosphates(mg/L)	Stannous chloride method	0.3mg/L
13	Sodium (mg/L)	Flame photometry	200mg/L
14	Potassium (mg/L)	Flame photometry	10mg/L
15	Heavy metal	Atomic absorption spectroscopy	Cu- 0.05mg/L Ni-10mg/L
16	SAR	Calculation	Less than 10
17	% Sodium	Calculation	Less than 60
18	RSC	Calculation	2.51 pm

3.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Physio-chemical result of groundwater

The Quality of ground water plays an important role in determining its suitability for various purposes such as Drinking, Domestic, Agriculture and Industry. Totally Twenty-seven groundwater samples were collected and analysed for fourteen different Physio-Chemical parameter such as pH, Electrical conductivity, TDS, Calcium, Magnesium, Total Hardness, Chlorides, pH, Sulphates, Phosphates, Nitrate, Fluorides and Electrical Conductivity, Heavy metals (Cu, Ni).

(Table 2). Descriptive statistics of groundwater samples

Parameters	Unit	Mean	Minimum	maximum
pH	--	6.84	6.39	8.9
E C	μS/cm	853.7	290	1870
TDS	mg/l	546.37	185.6	1196.8
T H	mg/l	302.59	110	700
NO3	mg/l	61.79	5.07	84.32
Ca	mg/l	72.89	24	172
Mg	mg/l	29.37	-2.44	84.18
Cl	mg/l	109.65	30.62	265.44
Alkalinity	mg/l	137.41	30	320
HCO3	mg/l	167.64	36.6	390.4
F	mg/l	0.08	0	0.29
Na+	mg/l	50.05	13.98	441.52
K+	mg/l	2.3	0.63	5.8
PO4	mg/l	0.66	0.29	1.5
SO4	mg/l	45.86	4.9	105.45
Cu	ppm	0.35	0.31	0.39
Ni	ppm	25.99	18.86	30.27
SAR	--	1.34	0.43	11.91
% sodium	%	24.35	9.79	78.5
RSC	meq/L	-3.31	-10.01	0.4

i) pH

The values of pH in the groundwater samples collected and analysed from the study area varied from 6.3 to 8.9 (Fig 4.1.3), indicating a slightly acidic to slightly basic nature. All the samples showed a pH value within the permissible limit of 6.5–8.5 (IS 10500:2012), except samples (sample No S5, S6, S8, S11), which showed a pH value crossing the permissible limit.

Fig. 2. pH Distribution in ground water sample

ii) Electrical conductivity

In the study area, the electrical conductivity (EC) of groundwater varies widely and ranges between 1.40 and 1.80 dS/m (Fig 4.1.4) against the standard permissible limit is from 0.7- 3.0 dS/m (IS 10500:2012).

Fig. 3. Distribution of EC in ground water sample

iii) Total dissolved solid

The total dissolved solids include bicarbonates, sulphates and chlorides of calcium, magnesium and sodium. Potassium, chloride, nitrate and boron form a minor part. The TDS in water samples include all salts in solution, but does not include suspended sediments, colloids or dissolved gases. The TDS values varied between 896 to 900mg/L (Fig 4.1.5) the permissible limit from 400-2000 mg/L (IS 10500:2012).

Fig. 4. Distribution of TDS in ground water sample.

iv) **Calcium and Magnesium**

It is an abundant constituent in groundwater. Ca and Mg constitute to the hardness of water. Calcium is abundantly available in rocks and soil. It is the main constituent of calcareous rocks. The solubility increases with temperature. Calcium hardness permissible limit for groundwater 01-20 mg/l (IS 10500:2012). In the present study, the calcium content ranged from in the ground water samples is 6.20 mg/l.

Fig. 5. Distribution of Calcium and Magnesium concentration in ground water sample.

Magnesium is abundant in dolomites, limestone, magnetite and ultrabasic rocks. Magnesium carbonates and double carbonates are made available from these rocks for solution. Magnesium salts concentration (Fig 4.1.8) in the ground water samples are 0-5 mg/l (IS 10500:2012).

v) **Sodium**

In the study area, the Sodium concentration (Na) in groundwater varied widely and ranges between 1.17 to 2.6 mg/l (Fig 4.1.9) while the leachate samples showed the concentration value crossing the permissible limit below 3.0 mg/l (IS 10500:2012).

Fig. 6. Distribution of Sodium in ground water sample

vi) **Bicarbonates**

In the study area, the Bicarbonate (HCO_3) of groundwater varies widely and ranges between 5.6 to 7 mg/l (Fig 4.1.11). The permissible limit for bicarbonates in 1.5 to 8.5mg/l.

Fig. 7. Distribution of Bicarbonate concentration in ground water sample

vii) Chloride

Chloride is most abundant and is an invariable constituent of groundwater. The chlorides are sparsely available in volcanic rocks and those contributed by magmatic springs. Chlorides are present in all natural waters. The Chloride value varies from 6.4 to 7 mg/l (Fig 4.1.12). The permissible limit of chloride concentrations is 4.0-10 mg/l.

Fig. 8. Distribution of Chloride in ground water sample

viii) SAR

The classification of groundwater samples from the study area with respect to SAR (Todd 1959). The SAR value of all the samples is found to be less than 10 and are classified as excellent for irrigation (Fig 4.1.19). The sodality index was calculated using the SAR, and was used for the classification of the groundwater samples. Based on the sodality index, all the samples belong to class 1. Spatial variation of SAR is shown in graph. The permissible limit for SAR is < 10.

Fig. 9. Distribution of SAR in ground water sample

ix) Residual sodium carbonate

According to the US Department of Agriculture, water having more than 2.50 epm of RSC is not suitable for irrigation purposes. The groundwater in the study area is classified on the basis of RSC and the results are presented in (Fig 4.1.21), the RSC values vary from the (-10 to 0.2), all the samples in the study area are within the permissible limit, and it's good for the irrigation.

3.2. Statistical analysis

The data collected from various locations were analysed with Megastat Software. Correlation analysis was performed and is elucidated in Table 6. The physico-chemical parameters and helps in establishing linkages through correlations between environmental, biological, and chemical variables.

The present study the pH is directly correlated with alkalinity, bicarbonate, and fluoride due to the high concentration of these parameter leads to increases in the pH. The HCO_3 is an alkaline buffering substance found in dentifrices, its indirectly effect on the fluoride in the ground water leads to the water turns to alkaline condition.

The Electrical conductivity is directly correlated with the TDS, Total hardness, Ca, Mg, Cl, Alkalinity, HCO_3 , K^+ and SO_4 . The salt content in the water is due to the presence of potassium, sodium, chloride, nitrate, sulphate etc. Extremely high values for conductivity are attributable to high levels of cations and anions. The cations and anions correlate with the conductivity in the water. The high amount of the salt content present in the ground water leads to the increases in the conductivity value. Electrical conductivity is an indicator of dissolved inorganic ions in ground water.

Total dissolved solids are correlated with the TH, Ca, Mg, Cl, Alkalinity, HCO_3 , K^+ and SO_4 . The present of the high inorganic ion in the groundwater reason for the TDS values. The present of the salts and the rock structure in the aquifer are main source of the entry of the all the inorganic salts and ions concentration in the ground water.

Total hardness is directly correlated with the Ca, Mg, Alkalinity, HCO_3 , K^+ and SO_4 content in the groundwater. The inorganic salts and cations concentration main source of the hardness in the ground water. The main Ca and Mg ions forms the complex in the groundwater result to increases in the salt concentration in the water. The bicarbonate, K^+ , SO_4 are the predominance source of hardness of water in the ground.

Calcium concentration is directly correlated with the Mg, Cl, and SO_4 . The Ca is directly combined with the Mg leads to increases in the Ca concentration. The Ca is cation they form bond with anion like Cl and SO_4 result to increases in the Ca concentration in the groundwater.

Magnesium is also the cation it is also directly correlated with the inorganic and anion salt present in water, Cl, Alkalinity, HCO_3 , K^+ , and SO_4 are main correlated factors. The Mg are in the alkaline form in the water so that the bicarbonate and alkalinity is directly correlated with the Mg concentration in water. The potassium and SO_4 are the predominance source of Mg concentration in groundwater.

Chloride is directly correlated with K^+ and SO_4 because the Cl are the anion compound, they combine with the K^+ and SO_4 ions forms the compound. And also increases the salinity in the ground water.

Alkalinity is correlated with Bicarbonates. Alkalinity is caused by bicarbonate, carbonate and hydroxyl ions. The biodegradation processes of organic matter produce significant amount of bicarbonate, which represents dissolved carbon dioxide which is also the major components of alkalinity.

Sodium is directly correlated with the SAR and % sodium in the water. The SAR measures the relative proportion of sodium ions., sodium ions tend to be absorbed by clay particles, displacing

Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions. This exchange process of Na⁺ in water for Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ in soil reduces the permeability and eventually results in soil with poor internal drainage. This reason the Na is directly correlated with SAR and %Na.

4.0. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present study showed that the groundwater quality at Kathige village is not fit for drinking as various water quality parameters were above the permissible limits (viz., TH, TDS, pH, Cl and Electrical Conductivity) but, the groundwater can be used for agricultural purposes. During the field survey, it was observed that the ground water is exhibiting a bad smell, possibly due to interaction with leachate. Even in the village, people have expressed opinion that they have been informed by the public health department not use water either for drinking or for cooking purpose. They are getting water for their day today requirements from far away places. People in the village also told that they are using the bore well water only for washing, clean in and gardening purposes. After people's objection to stop disposing the municipal solid waste disposal site about 4 years back, the area is not receiving the waste from various parts of the Davangere city. To overcome this problem, people have to do artificial recharging of groundwater by different rainwater harvesting methods which will in turn reduces the pollution level in the groundwater in the village and surrounding areas.

The samples S1 and S4 are the major contaminated samples presents in Kathige landfill area surrounding. The samples cross the pH, EC, TDS, slightly Alkaline, TH, Chloride, Nitrate, Phosphate, and trace metals concentration all the present in the core zone with in the 1km away from the dumpsite. The ground water is directly influenced by the landfill site, and contaminates are directly entrance the ground water through the percolation process. This study mainly concluded that the groundwater physico-chemical parameters are slightly cross the permissible limit but the trace metals and Phosphate, Nitrate excided the permissible limit. Based on the SAR, percent sodium, and RSC values, all the ground water samples having the good and excellent quality and can be suitable for the all the irrigation and domestic uses. But on the other hand, the trace metal concentration is slightly above from the WHO (1998) and IPCS (1991) standards and could have possible health impact on long run.

The past five-year study report of the groundwater quality of the Kathige village has exceeded the BIS standard limit, mainly happened during the disposal of municipal solid waste in the village which led to the contamination of the ground water, and the effect was retained up to the 3years. Based on the present study, it is evident that the groundwater quality is relatively good over past five years results done by the Department of Mines and Geology, The Fisheries Research and Information Centre, Hebbal, Bangalore. It can be finally concluded that the groundwater is returning to its original quality status after the ban of dumping solid waste.

Recommendation and suggestions

- The sample size should be increased to understand the actual scenario of the contamination entering the groundwater resources.
- If the all-trace metal concentration is analysed in groundwater, clear cut idea on total metal load due to the leachate contamination can be established.
- Regular monitoring of the groundwater should be encouraged to avoid possible consumption of contaminated foodstuff and drinking water.
- Proper legislation on the handling of municipal solid waste should be introduced to forestall waste related problems along the food chain.
- Modern waste disposal facilities should be acquired by the authorities concerned and appropriate waste disposal sites chosen by experts to avoid the ground water contamination.

- Recycling and sorting of wastes before dumping can also help to reduce the trace metal concentration in ground water.
- Adopting modern engineering techniques for the management of the waste's disposal site could reduce the pollution load in groundwater and air.
- Following the waste management 5R rules in the lifestyle would help to reduce the solid waste production and problems related waste management.
- Support to modern engineering technology and models for the production of the methane gas by using the leachate as the raw material, reduce the leachate related problems.

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